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Attitude toward Business and Business Intention of ABM and STEM Students of Senior High School of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region, Philippines: The Role of Education

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to determine the level of attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and their business intention and to find out if there is a difference of attitude toward business and business intention of both strands (ABM and STEM). To establish the theories of the study, the literature was reviewed. The study used descriptive correlational research design and to gather the data, the validated questionnaires were used. The population of the study was grade XII ABM and STEM students of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The study found that their attitude toward business and their business intention is high and based on Pearson r correlation, it was found that there is a significant correlation between attitude toward business and business intention and therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. However, based on the F-test which measures the difference between the attitude of ABM and STEM students' attitude toward business and their business intention, the study found that there is no significant difference between both strands when it comes to their attitude toward business and their business intention.

Keywords. Attitude, cognitive, affective, business intention

Introduction/Rationale

Hill and Stone (2009) in their book, entitled, "Success Through a Positive Mental Attitude" emphasize one important point that a positive mental attitude will attract the good and the beautiful, while the negative attitude will rob you of all that makes life worth living. In short, success, health, happiness and wealth are all depending on how you make up your mind. This theory applies to all human endeavours. Success will depend on our attitude toward what we are doing. This has the same meaning as McCloud (2017) when he argued that success is a product of a positive attitude. Happiness and fulfilment in life can be achieved by changing our attitude from negative to positive thinking. Ajzen (1993) would argue that attitude is a key predictor toward behaviour, in the sense that attitude will always lead to a certain behaviour. It is not an overstatement if Harrel (2009) would argue that attitude is everything. Attitude, whether positive or negative has the power to impact individual behaviour and individual

success in life. By having a positive attitude, one can create a positive environment, achieve goals or career success, increase productivity level, overcome challenges, etc.

Attitude affects the career choice of a person (Nakagomi, Hayashi, & Komiyama, 2016, Llopis, 2011). Based on those findings, we can also argue that the attitude of students toward business may affect their choice to go into business. There have been no studies yet related to the cognitive and affective attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and its effect on business intention and the difference of attitude toward business and business intention of ABM and STEM students. Their business intention. The current study intends to pursue the gap and to provide an idea about how student attitude toward business may affect their plan to do business in the future and to find out the difference between the attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and Pursuing such purpose, we would like to find out the attitude of students of Divine Word Colleges toward business particularly those who are taking up business management subjects and with those who are not taking business management subjects.

The Importance of the Study

It cannot be denied that life cannot be improved without business. The business affects not only personal life but it affects family life, community life and the country's life (Unicef, 2012). The country does not progress without people who have an entrepreneurial attitude and have the interest to go into business. Therefore the study is intended to measure students' attitudes toward business and their intention to go into business and the difference of attitude toward business and business intention of ABM and STEM students. The output of the study can be used as a source of information for the curriculum developer of the school to design curriculum and activities that can change and improve the attitude of students toward business and it may help to improve the teaching strategy of teachers who are handling the ABM and STEM strands.

Literature Review

In my previous research on attitude, several figures such as Allport (1968) and Ajzen (1993) have emphasized that attitude matters to behaviour. Human behaviour is influenced by his views or philosophy in life, perceptions, and feelings toward certain objects, person or problems. Each person has different attitudes toward certain objects, person or problems. One person may have a positive attitude toward the same objects or persons, while others may see the same object or person negatively. Thus the way how they deal or relate to the object or person is different from one person to another. Consequently, one might be enthusiastically dealing with the object or the person, while the other tries to avoid as much as possible. The same kind of attitude also affects how people see problems. One problem can be viewed from two sides of view, positively and negatively. One person may see a problem positively, as a challenge, while the other person may see the problem as something to be avoided.

Attitude is responsible for making a difference among people. Though two people or more have the same capability, the output they produce may not be the same because they have a different attitude. It answers the question of why one is more successful than the other (Maxwell, 2006). Harrel (2009) goes further to explain why one organization is more successful than the other because of the attitude of human beings who are working in it. According to her, attitude, whether it is positive or negative, has the power to impact the organization's success. Attitude is a matter of mental conditioning. It is about what you think and feels about certain objects, person or problems and it is what you think and feels that will influence your behaviour.

Success is not always contributed by skills, experience, and money but it is about our mind positioning. This is what Trump and Zanker (2009) mean when they say "Think Big".

Dreaming high is a source of inspiration for someone to work. Money is not a problem when someone wants to succeed in life but the right mind and right attitude. There are many ways on how someone can find the capital of his business but that should not be the main concern and hindrance for going into business as long as one has the idea and ambition to go into business. This is what Samuel (2008) means when he says that all is mind. Many millionaires do not start their business with big money but with dreams and passion to pursue the dreams. It has been always said that change the way one thinks can make a difference in life and our thoughts can create reality (Ling, p.11). It is recognized that our thought has the power to make things happen and can create the life one desires.

The Divine Word Colleges open business course and the purpose of the opening course in business are to produce entrepreneurs in the future. Many students have been taking the course and therefore they are prepared to go into business. However, the concern that lingers in the mind is that if this course influences the attitude of students toward business and then plan to do business in the future. If this course prepares students to go into business, how about other courses? Finding the difference in the attitude toward business and business intention of students of different strands will determine the relevance and the importance of business course.

Human Attitude and Its Origin

Human attitude is a reaction toward certain objects, persons, problems or events. Such reaction can be in the form of ideas or thoughts and feelings toward such a particular object, person, problem or events or other discriminable aspects of the individual's world (Ajzen, 1993). This is the definition that we hold in this paper as Ajzen (1993) argued that there are a lot of definitions of attitude from different theorists, but from those definitions, there is a common denominator among them that attitude has its evaluative dimension (Bem, 1970, Edwards, 1957, Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). All agree that though attitude is in the mind of the person but it can be measured and evaluated through the behaviour of the person. Behaviour is an expression of the person of what is inside his mind. As Ajzen (1993 cited by Abun, 2019) argued that though attitude is hidden or latent it can be measured through the responses of the person toward the object of the attitude. The reaction toward that object can positive or favourable or negative or unfavourable. Ajzen (1993), Allport (1954), Hilgard (1980), Rosenberg and Hoyland (1960) classified three categories of reaction or responses and they are ***cognitive, affective and conative responses***. These are manifestations of latent attitude which is unobservable by human eyes (Ajzen, 1993). First, the ***Cognitive component*** is the beliefs and thoughts about the subject, the object, the person, the institution, the event, etc. It is the ideas of the person toward the subject, object or person, etc. Second, ***the affective component*** of attitude is the feeling of the person toward the subject, object or person, etc. It is how one reacts emotionally when he/she is confronting the subject, object, person or institution. It is still a psychological reaction which may be a verbal or nonverbal expression of feelings toward the subject, object, person or the institution (Abun, 2019). Such a reaction may be a negative feeling or a positive feeling toward such an object. In other words, the person is happy or not happy, excited or not excited after being confronted with such objects, or person or problems. Lastly, ***the conative component*** of attitude is about how attitude affects one's behaviour. These may include plans, intentions, and commitments to a planned behaviour. These are the three components of attitude and therefore, attitude is a multidimensional construct (Abun, 2019, cited from Ajzen, 1993).

The discussion on the origin of attitude has been presented by several authors. According to Ajzen (1993), attitude is not just automatically born in the mind of the person but it is a result of exposure or experience. For example, Ajzen (1993) explained that a person

develops such an attitude perhaps as a result of watching a television program or some other kind of exposures or experiences. Concerning such an idea, Abun (2017) does not point out exposure as the main culprit of the origin of attitude but it is the culture. He explained his position in his article on the environmental attitude and environmental behaviour of employees, that culture is the one to be blamed for destructive behaviour. In his argument, he pointed out that though the environmental problem is a result of human behaviour, however, such destructive human behaviour is originated from the culture. He further pointed out that solving the environmental problem is to review the destructive culture that has influenced the mind of people toward the environment. It cannot be denied that a person is raised and developed in a certain culture and such culture is responsible to form the mind of people within that culture. This argument is based on the ideas of anthropologists such as Donald (2002), Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995). Donald (2002) explained that culture is playing an important role in our brain functioning and even brain structure. Culture influences brain functioning to a great extent as she argued that culture has a direct impact on our brains and affect the major part of the brains. Culture effectively wires up the functional subsystem in the brain.

The idea of culture and its effect on brain functioning indicates the power of culture in the formation of the brain and ideas of people about everything around them that affect them (Abun, 2018). Abun's view and Donald's view is similar to Hofstede's view as cited by Brown (1995) when he argued that culture is the collective programming of the human mind that distinguishes the members of one human group from one culture of another. Hofstede pointed out clearly that culture is expressed in how people think or view things. To elaborate on the idea of Hofstede, Amstrong (1996) contend that there is a relationship between cultural dimensions and ethical perceptions. In other words, an ethical attitude is formed by a particular culture. One perceives a certain object, subject, person or institution to be negative or positive, favourable or not favourable because he/she has been taught by the culture of a particular society where he/she is living. What he/she learns from the culture will be his/her ideas about a certain subject, object or events, etc. that he/she will encounter.

The Relationship between Human Attitude and Human Behaviour

We try to borrow the psychological concept to explain the relationship between human attitude and human behaviour. This is not to problematize the concept but to use its concept in the current study. In psychology, an attitude is understood as a set of emotions, beliefs, and behaviours toward a particular object, person, thing, or event (Banaji & Heiphetz, 2010). Those emotions, beliefs, and behaviours are not just spontaneous reactions but it is a learned reaction. As Cherry (2019) argued that those reactions are learned tendency to perceived things in a certain way. Thus, reactions may not necessarily be the same. One can have a positive or negative evaluation or perception of certain objects, experiences, practices, etc. These reactions are caused by the exposure or experience the person has related to the object, person, problems or events. It is not an isolated reaction but it is connected to the experience. Mostly believe that those attitudes are the results of experience, upbringing/education, and social interactions. Cherry (2019) further contends that experience or upbringing or education can have a powerful influence over attitudes. Since attitude is not independent of environment or experience, thus it is also accepted that attitudes are dynamics in the sense that it is enduring and the same time it can also be changed (Abun, 2019). The attitude of the person toward a certain object, person, problems or events may change if the object of attitude has changed.

Controversies on the relationship between attitude and behaviour have started early days. The main concern of the controversy was about attitude if the attitude is a key predictor toward behaviour. Originally the early researchers on the relationship between attitude and

behaviour consistently found the relationship between attitude and behaviour and based on their findings, people have accepted as a given that attitude influenced the behaviour (Thomas & Znaniecki, 1918, Watson, 1925). This idea was taken for granted for quite some time until the time that later studies proved otherwise. Some investigators challenged the earlier findings through field studies on the relationship between attitude and behaviour. Later studies found that there was no correlation or little correlation between attitude and behaviour. Take some examples such as Corey (1937), Freeman & Ataoev, (1960) as cited by Ajzen (1993) conducted a study on the college students' attitude at the beginning of the semester and provide multiple opportunities to cheat by allowing them to score their test. His test found that there was no correlation between students' attitude and their cheating behaviour (Ajzen, 1993, p.74). Studies after Corey (1937), Freeman and Ataoey (1960) supported their findings. For example, Dean (1958) conducted a study on attitude toward labour unions and participating in labour union meetings, and his study found no correlation. A similar study in support of this finding was also done by Wicker and Pomazal, (1971) as cited by Abun (2019) on the attitude toward participating in a subject in social psychology and actual participation in a social psychology class. Their studies found no correlation.

Strengthening the findings of “no correlation between attitude and behaviour” was the study of Wicker (1969). His study still negated the original findings that attitude is a key predictor of behaviour. His study and other studies (Wicker & Pomazal, 1971, Dean, 1958) have strengthened the idea that there is no correlation between attitude and behaviour. The results of those studies lead to the de-appreciation of the importance of studying personal disposition and behaviour. As a result, by the 1970s most social psychologists accepted the negative verdict of the relationship between attitude and behaviour. Researchers started changing their focus and directions. Instead of studying the relationship between attitude and behaviour, they encouraged the study of social context and norms as a determinant factor in predicting behaviour or human action (De Fleur & Westie, 1958, Deutscher, 1969).

However, interest in the study on the relationship between attitude and behaviour was renewed by other social psychologists, particularly Ajzen and Fishbein (1977, 2000,) Based on their study, they still maintain that attitude is still key to predict the behaviour and their findings were supported by other social psychologists such as Allport (1968). Allport (1968) still considered attitude to be "the most distinctive and indispensable concept in contemporary American social psychology" (p. 59). Against other social psychologists who were against the finding of early research, they argued that the inconsistencies are not with the attitude and behaviour itself, but other factors or circumstances. It may happen because of many factors such as response biases, the multidimensionality of attitudes, and moderating variables. In terms of response biases, they argue that there is a tendency to give socially desirable responses on attitude and personality inventories and along with this point, they recommended the need to use attitude measures that are less subject to systematic biases (Ajzen, 1993). Concerning the multidimensionality of attitudes, they pointed out that most attitude measurement technique resulted in a single score representing the respondent's overall positive or negative reaction to the attitude object. According to them, focus on a single dimension did not do justice to the complexity of the attitude construct (Allport, 1935). Single construct is against attitude as a multidimensional construct which includes cognition, affective and conation component (Rosenberg & Hovland, 1960). Lastly, the inconsistencies are due to moderating variables. They argued that the degree of attitude-behaviour consistency was assumed to be moderated by factors related to the person performing the behaviour such as self-awareness, self-efficacy, self-monitoring, experience, self-confidence, even feeling and lack of information or

knowledge. They also pointed out the situation as moderating variables such as time pressure or circumstances surrounding the performance of the behaviour (Ajzen, 1993).

The recent studies conducted by Abun, et.al. (2018) and Fitzsimmons and Douglas (2005) have strengthened the findings of Ajzen (1993) and Allport (1968). Their studies support the consistency of the influence of attitude toward behaviour. Abun, et.al. (2018) measured the relationship between environmental attitude and environmental behaviour and his study found that environmental attitude predicted the environmental behaviour of the students and employees toward the environment. A similar study on the relationship between attitude and behaviour was also done. He conducted a study on the entrepreneurial attitude and future intention to establish a business and the finding of the study also indicated a correlation between attitude and behavioural intention. Concerning the findings, Fitzsimmons and Douglas (2005) in their study also found that entrepreneurial attitudes are significant in explaining career decisions in the future and their intention to go into business.

Business Attitude and attitude toward business

We go back to the concept of attitude before we present our views about the attitude toward business so that we place our concept of attitude toward business within the understanding of attitude. Attitude is an individual concept or idea and feelings toward certain objects or persons or problem and it has been recognized that such idea or feeling influences individual behaviour toward that particular person, object or problems (Ajzen, 1993). Attitude toward certain objects or person or problem can be positive and negative and this positive or negative attitude can affect the way how the person reacts or responds to that particular objects, person or problem and this is the affective component of the attitude (Allport (1954), Hilgard (1980), Rosenberg and Hoyland (1960). Ajzen (1993) have pointed out that the reason why there is a positive and negative idea or feeling toward certain objects, persons or problems or events is because of exposure or experience that the person has encountered. Donald (2002) even blame the culture as the source of ideas or feelings toward certain objects, person or events or problems. Hofstede, as cited by Brown (1995), pointed out culture is the one responsible for the formation of the human brain.

It is recognized that attitude is crucial to the success of our work, whatever work we are in, whether we are in the teaching job, public office or private business. The right attitude is needed as pointed by Sykes (2018), an expert in Entrepreneur and Penny Stocks. He argued that the easy way to be happy and successful is to change our attitude from negative to positive attitude. He pointed out a "can-do attitude" is necessary to accomplish business objectives. This is confirmed by Rohn (2017), a personal development expert, that having the right attitude is important for business success, as he argued that moving toward success is not a matter of skills or experience in work but the first skill that people need to hone is attitude. Positive results will always need a positive attitude and therefore, one should try to shift his/her thoughts and create a positive attitude (Hansen, 2016). Harrel (2016) pointed out one of the attitudes that lead us to success namely enthusiasm or staying positive. One should create a burning desire and commitment to achieve one's goal. Evans Kerrigan, Integris Performance Advisors as cited by Pirouz (2017) said that to be successful in business, one must maintain a "winner's attitude" which is to always learn something new and seek feedback from others to grow and improve.

Business attitude and attitude toward business are two important viewpoints that one needs to distinguish. Business attitude is related to the entrepreneurial attitude which has something to do with risk-taking, enthusiasm, ambitions, etc. but the attitude toward business is how one sees and feels toward the business in terms of positive and negative view or feeling toward business. The success of a business is not just a matter of having the right attitude but it has something to do with attitude toward business. One can go into business when he/she has a

positive view of the business. Wallens (1976) had conducted a study and had recognized that attitude toward business, industry, and work are crucial determinants to business success and the community's prosperity. In his study, he compared the different attitudes of people of different developed countries toward business and he found that among those countries being investigated, Britain was the one most dependent on the success of the industry and business for prosperity but a large part of Britain's population was considered anti-business. The British were not only critical to business but they were hostile to business and therefore, he emphasized that nations need to have a pro-business attitude to prosper and grow. A similar study was also done by Patwardhan, et.al (2012). They conducted a study and compared the attitude of Hispanics and Anglos in America toward business and they found that Hispanics have a more negative attitude toward business than the Anglos do. Their negative attitude is somehow is connected to their religious background. Wang and Yang (2011) investigated the attitude of Muslim's attitude toward business in China and both have found that Muslim business people have different attitudes toward business such as socially detached, socially engaged, pragmatic, traditionalist and secular. Muslim business people who are considered socially detached believe that business makes them impure and therefore, they should detach themselves from the business because business can cause them to go astray and against Muslim principles. However, those who are seen as socially engaged view business very positively. They view business as part of their religious calling and their study found that these are the people who are charged with the spirit of capitalism and venture into a non-traditional business venture. While practical Muslim businesspeople view business as a means to survive economically. Lastly, traditional Muslim businesspeople regard business as a tradition of their ancestors and therefore it is a natural choice for them to continue to do traditional business such as sheepskin wholesale, and halal restaurant.

In the Philippine context, mostly Filipinos view business positively and considered business as a reliable means to improve one's economic and social standing (Reyes, 2015 cited from The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor/GEM). Such a positive attitude is prompted by the positive economic environment of the country and Filipinos see business as a means of gaining popularity. Media exposure to entrepreneurs seems to serve as one of the motivating factors why people are motivated to go into business. This positive view on business may have been also influenced by their view toward money, that money is a means of life security and pleasure. Through money, one can secure his future life and enjoy the life they want to enjoy such as enjoying good food (Angel, 2012). As a result of money as a means of pleasure is the Filipino spends too much over their means and as a result of the attitude of "you live only once" (Juan, 2018). This prompts the DepEd, along with the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) and Banco De Oro Foundation (BDOF), to integrate into the curriculum financial education and to create and disseminate learning materials on proper financial management to the public schools nationwide (Montemayor, 2018).

Attitude toward Business is Key predictor of business intention

Attitude is defined as the way how a person responds positively or negatively toward a certain idea, object, person or situation. It influences individual choices of action (Cherry, 2020). It becomes a key factor in understanding the behaviour of a person. As it has been argued that attitude is an important factor to understand the extent of the behaviour of a person. No less than Allport (1968) argued that attitude is a key factor to understand behaviour. In the same sense, we also argue that attitude toward business is a key factor to determine the intention of a person to do business in the future. There have been a lot of studies related to the entrepreneurial attitude of students and their entrepreneurial intention to do business in the future. The results

of these studies indicated that there is a correlation between entrepreneurial attitude and how such attitude is correlated to business intention or entrepreneurship (De Lange, (2000), Fitzsimmons & Douglas, (2005), Venesaar, (2006), Ndivhuho Tshikovhi & Shambare, (2015), Abun, 2018). However, studies related to attitude toward business and business intention are not many yet but growing interest in that field is significant. Based on these studies, students have seen business positively as a means for employment and the improvement of society's life. Take for an example of Okeke (2016). He assessed business students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship and their entrepreneurial intention. The study found that that most of the final year students in the department of business administration in GSU (Gombe State University, Nigeria) have a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship and many of them would prefer to be entrepreneurs upon completion of their study. He even went further to recommend the University Administrator to bring into the lecture environment several successful entrepreneurs to share their experiences with the students. The positive attitude toward business was also shown by the students in India as pointed out by the study of Manishal and Singh (2016) and students from Africa as found by Abualbasal and Badran (2019). Their studies found that students see business as a means to improve society's life and individual life. This is also confirmed by the study of Venesaar, et.al (2006) and Niljinda, et.al (2017). Students' positive attitude toward entrepreneurship influences their desire to go into business in the future, though it may not be immediately after graduation. The reason why a person goes into a business can vary from one person to another. For example, Terfa (2007) pointed out in his study that students have seen business or entrepreneurship as a way to be independent, helping to create employment and improving society's life. This is also seen in the study of Kgagara (2011) as he pointed out that the main reason why young Africans plan to go into business is to improve the life of society and provide employment. The interest of students in business or entrepreneurship can be correlated to business knowledge and family background with business as pointed by the study of Wang and Wong (2004).

Economic growth cannot be achieved unless there is growth in business or entrepreneurship because without it no economic development and prosperity can be attained. Economic growth can also be separated from the business interest of people to go into business. Business interest is a result of how people see business. People's attitude toward business is crucial to the realization of economic growth. Researchers have tried to discover the reason why some people go into business and why some don't. This is tied to the individual's attitude toward business. Bardeba, et.al (2012) conducted a study about the attitude of students toward entrepreneurship and the study found that students have a very positive attitude toward business and this attitude had influenced their intention to go into business in the future. Discussion on attitude toward business has evolved into a discussion on the reason why a person goes into business. Motivation to go into business may not necessarily be for economic reasons. Self-independence has been pointed out as one of the reasons why people decide to be an entrepreneur. Besides, Mahfud, et.al (2019) found that social and psychological capital are also other reasons why people go into business. Their study found that entrepreneurial attitude orientation, social capital, and psychological capital collaboratively and interactively influence the entrepreneurial intention of polytechnic students in Jogjakarta. Specifically, the study found that psychological capital was shown to have a positive partial mediation effect on the relationship between entrepreneurial attitude orientation and entrepreneurial intention. Psychological capital was also found to fully mediate the impact of social capital on entrepreneurial intention. Cavus & Kapusuz, (2015), Luthans, et.al (2007) defined psychological capital as a condition of positive individual psychological development characterized by self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience. Self-efficacy refers to one's self-

confidence in performing the job (Cavus & Kapusuz, 2015). Optimism is a psychological intention to expect something good (Cavus & Kapasuz, 2015). While hope means expectations that inspire people to achieve their goals (Luthans & Youssef, 2004). And lastly, resilience is defined as the ability to adapt to facing risk or significant difficulties (Luthans & Youssef, 2004). The study of Venesaar, et.al (2006) and Riquelme, et.al (2019) support the finding of Mahfud, et. Al (2019). Their study found that personal characteristics have something to do with the attitude of students toward business and their intention to go into business. They found that the personal characteristics or psychological capital and behaviour typical of entrepreneurs are correlated positively to start a new venture shortly.

Concerning social capital, the study of Padwardhan, et.al (2012) even pointed out that religiosity also affects the attitude of people toward business. His study showed that Hispanic Americans who are majority Catholics have a negative attitude toward business compared to Anglo – Americans. A similar study conducted among Muslims in China by Wang and Yang (2011). Their study identified four attitudes of Muslims toward business and they are socially detached, socially engaged, pragmatic, traditionalist and secular. Socially detached people see business negatively because it goes against their religion. One has to detach themselves from the business. Socially engaged business people believed that business is necessary and it is part of their religious calling. While pragmatic Muslims view business as a means for survival. This group belongs to the fundamentalist group of Islam. On the other side, the traditionalist believes that business as part of their job to continue the practice of their ancestors and most of them are engaging in traditional business such as sheepskin wholesale and halal restaurants. Lastly, the secular group. This group believes that religion and business are two separate things. The group tends to view Islam as the cultural heritage of their ethnic group.

Lastly, a study also found that a negative attitude toward business is not only found among people who are religious as we have cited above but the negative attitude toward business is also found in advanced countries, except Japan. For example, Wellens (1976) conducted a study and compare the attitude of people from advanced countries such as France, England, and Japan. His study found that out of all the advanced nations included in the study, Britain is the one most dependent for prosperity on the success of her industry and business and yet “large sections of her populace have attitude sets which can accurately be described as anti-business, they are not merely critical of business but are hostile”. Despite the benefits, they have enjoyed business and industry but they still have a negative attitude toward business. They are supposed to be appreciating the value of the business but their attitude toward business is otherwise. Wellens (1976) did not point out the reason why such a negative attitude occurred among the people of Britain.

Conceptual Framework
Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

Source: Abun, et.al. (2019)

Figure1: The conceptual framework reflects the concept of the study. It indicates that cognitive and affective attitude are dependent variables and behavioural intention to conduct business is the dependent variable. It shows that cognitive and affective attitude toward business correlates to the behavioural intention to establish a business in the future. The correlation between attitude toward business and business intention is aided by the educational background.

Statement of the Problems

The purpose of the study is to find out the influence of cognitive and affective attitude of students toward business and their future business intention. It specifically answers the following questions:

1. What is the attitude of students toward business in terms of
 - a. Cognitive attitude
 - b. Affective attitude?
2. What is the future business intention of the students?
3. Is there a correlation between the attitude of students toward business and future business intention?
4. Is there a relationship between educational background and business Intention?
5. Is there a difference between the cognitive and affective attitude and business intention of ABM and STEM students?

Assumption of the Study

Ajzen and Fishbein, (2000) argued that attitude is a predictor of behaviour. Based on their theory, the current study assumes that the attitude of students toward business affects their future intention to establish a business. The study also assumes that attitude and intention can be measured and the answer to the questionnaires are objective.

Hypothesis

Based on the theory of Ajzen and Fishbein (2000) that there is a correlation between attitude and behaviour, therefore the current study hypothesized that cognitive and affective attitude of students toward business correlates to their future business intention. It is also argued that there is a difference between ABM and STEM strands students' attitude toward business and their business intention.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of the study is all the Divine Word Colleges in Region I that offer hotel and restaurant management courses. It limits its investigation only to attitude toward business particularly cognitive and affective attitude and the business intention.

Methodology

The study was conducted to investigate the correlation between attitude toward business and business intention of student and it followed the appropriate research methodologies such as research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The study used a descriptive correlational research design. The nature of descriptive research is to describe what is found in the data collected through questionnaires and statistical treatment. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situation, phenomena or related variables. In short, it describes "what is" about the data (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019).

In line with the current study, the descriptive correlational method was deployed. The study determines the level of cognitive and affective attitude toward business and its correlation with the plan to establish a business in the future. This was to determine what the dominant attitude of students toward business was and what particular attitudes affect the behavioural intention to do business in the future.

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was the Divine Word College of Vigan and Divine Word and Divine Word College of Laoag. Divine Word College of Vigan is belonged to the Province of Ilocos Sur and located within the heritage city of Vigan. Divine Word College of Laoag is located at Ilocos Norte Province, a neighbouring province of Ilocos Sur. The Divine Word Colleges are run by the Congregation of the Divine Word Missionaries or known as Society of the Divine Word or in Latin, Societas Verbi Divini (SVD).

Population

The population of the study was composed of all grade XI and XII ABM and STEM students of Divine Word College of Vigan and Divine Word College of Laoag. Since the total numbers of students are limited, and therefore total enumeration is the sampling design of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study utilized validated questionnaires. The questionnaires were adapted from the work of Goel, et.al (2006) on the Attitude of youth toward entrepreneurship in China and India and the work of Venesaar (2006) on the attitude and intention of students toward entrepreneurship.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent a letter to the President of the College, requesting him to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in the college. The researcher personally met the President and students were requested to answer the questionnaires. The questionnaires were distributed through google forms and the advisers of ABM and STEM were requested to collect the answers from the students through their email.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In consistence with the study as descriptive research, therefore descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean is used to determine the level of cognitive and affective attitude of students toward business and behavioural intention to conduct business in the future. Pearson r was used to measure the correlation of attitudes toward corruption and the behavioural intention to corrupt or not to corrupt. While F-test was used to determine its differences in the attitude toward business and business intention of ABM and STEM students. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Empirical Data and Analysis

As an empirical and scientific study, a study must be supported by data that has been treated statistically. Thus, this part presents the data gathered through research questionnaires and the data presentation follows the structure of the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1: 1. What is the attitude of students toward business in terms of

a. Cognitive attitude

b? Affective attitude?

Table 1. The Cognitive Attitude of Students towards Business

Cognitive Component	Mean	DR
1. Business is better than working for others.	3.69	A
2. Business people are popular among my friends and family members.	3.64	A
3. Business people have a better life than others.	3.25	SWA
4. Rewards from business are better compared to other kinds of works.	3.22	SWA
5. Business people are respected in my society.	3.95	A
6. Business create employment for others.	4.30	A
7. Business people are richer than people who are employed by others.	3.34	SWA
8. Business people gain a better position in society.	3.47	A
9. Business people are their own master.	3.90	A
10. Only business people can make the country grow economically.	2.80	SWA
Composite Mean	3.56	A

Source: Goel, et.al (2006)

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *Strongly agree/Very High*
 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat agree/Moderate*
 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low/*

As gleaned from the data presented on the table, it shows that as a whole, the attitude of students toward business in terms of cognitive attitude toward business gained a composite mean of 3.56 which is interpreted as “agree/high”. This composite mean indicates that as a whole the cognitive attitude of students toward business is not very low, low or moderate but it is considered high. This suggests that students highly understand the extent of the importance of business to the life of individual people and society. However, when the items are taken singly, some items are rated as "somewhat agree/moderate" such as "business people have a better life than others (3.25), rewards from business are better compared to other kinds of work (3.22), business people are richer than people who are employed by others (3.34), and only business people can make the country economically" (2.80). While some other items are rated as "agree/high" such as "business is better than working for others (3.69), business people are popular among my friends and family members (3.64), business people are respected in my society (3.95), business create employment for others (4.30), Business people gain a better position in society (3.47) and business people are their own master” (3.90)

Table 2. The Affective Attitude of Students towards Business

<i>Affective Attitude toward Business</i>	Mean	DR
1. I love business because I have been raised in a family of businesspeople.	3.17	SWA
2. I am excited to go into business because it will provide a better life.	3.73	A
3. I am not afraid to go into business even if I might be losing money.	3.31	SWA
4. I like a business because I have been exposed to the family business.	3.18	SWA
5. I am confident to do business because I know about it.	3.42	A
6. I feel secure if I have my own business.	3.74	A
7. I am excited to go into business because I am free to make some innovations.	3.73	A
8. I am excited to go into business because it challenges my capability.	3.98	A
9. I am happy to be a businessman/woman because I can have my own life that I want	3.92	A
10. I feel good when I can help to employ others in the business.	4.28	A
11. I am happy when I am recognized as a businessman/woman.	3.99	A
Composite Mean	3.68	A

Source: Goel, et.al (2006)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low/</i>

Based on data presented in table 2, it reveals that as a whole, students attitude toward business in terms of affective attitude obtained a composite mean of 3.68 which means “agree/high”. This mean rating pointed out that as a whole the attitude of students toward business in terms of affective attitude or feelings toward business is not very low, low or moderate but it is considered high. It means that students highly like business emotionally because of what it can provide to the life of people and what it means to their personal life. Even when the items are taken separately, the majority of the items are evaluated within the mean range of "agree/high" such as “feeling excited to go into business because it will provide a better life (3.73), feeling secure if I have my own business (3.74), feeling happy to be a businessman/woman because I can have my own life that I want (3.92), feeling good when I can help to employ others in the business (4.28), feeling happy when I am recognized as a businessman/woman (3.99), feeling confident to do business because I know about it (3.42), feeling excited to go into business because I am free to make some innovations (3.73), and feeling excited to go into business because it challenges my capability (3.98). While some items are rated within the mean range of “somewhat agree/moderate” such as “loving business because I have been raised in a family of businesspeople (3.17), not being afraid to go into business even if I might be losing money (3.30), and as a business, because I have been exposed to the family business” (3.31).

Problem 2: What is the future business intention of students?

Table 3. The Future Business Intention of Students

<i>Business Intention</i>	Mean	DR
1. I will become an entrepreneur in the future so that I can be independent.	3.79	A
2. I will go into business to enjoy the life I want to live in.	3.69	A
3. I will go into business to earn a good income.	3.94	A
4. I will establish my own business so that I can realize my goals in life.	3.76	A
Composite Mean	3.79	A

Source: Venesaar (2006)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low/</i>

As presented on the table, it displays that as a whole, the future business intention of students gained a composite mean rating of 3.79 which is understood as "agree/high". It demonstrates that as a whole students' future business intention is not very low, low or moderate but their future business intention is high. Such finding suggests that students' probability to go into business is high. Students have known business to be advantageous to their life. Even if the

items are taken separately, all items are rated within the same mean range with the interpretation of “agree/high” such as “becoming an entrepreneur in the future so that I can be independent (3.79), going into business to enjoy the life I want to live in (3.69), going into business to earn good income (3.94) and establishing my own business so that I can realize my goals in life (3.76).

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between the attitude of students toward business and future business intention?

Table 4. Relationship between cognitive attitude, affective attitude and Educational background (ABM, STEM) towards business intentions

		BUSINESS INTENTION
EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND	Pearson Correlation	-.355**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	185
COGNITIVE ATTITUDE	Pearson Correlation	.505**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	186
AFFECTIVE ATTITUDE	Pearson Correlation	.756**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	186

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As presented in Table 3 concerning the correlation between attitude toward business and business intention, the Pearson r correlation table manifests that students’ attitude toward business is significantly correlated at 0.01 level (2-tailed) to their future business intention. Even when the variables are taken separately, both, cognitive and affective attitude, are correlated to future business intention. This finding recommends that to improve the business intention of the students, a change of attitude toward business is important.

Problem 4: is there a correlation between educational backgrounds such as ABM and STEM and business intention?

Table 4. Relationship between Educational background (ABM and STEM) and business intentions

		BUSINESS INTENTION
EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND (ABM & STEM)	Pearson Correlation	-.355**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	185
COGNITIVE ATTITUDE	Pearson Correlation	.505**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	186
AFFECTIVE ATTITUDE	Pearson Correlation	.756**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	186

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the Pearson r correlation table about the correlation between education and future business intention of students, it shows that education is significantly correlated to the future business intention. Both courses such as ABM (Accounting, Business and Management) and STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) are significantly correlated to future business intention.

Problem 5: Is there a difference between the cognitive and affective attitude and business intention of ABM and STEM students?

Table 5. The Differences in cognitive attitude, affective attitude and business intentions between ABM and STEM students.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
BI	Between Groups	18.602	1	18.602	26.379	.000
	Within Groups	129.047	183	.705		
	Total	147.649	184			
CA	Between Groups	4.643	1	4.643	15.176	.000
	Within Groups	55.987	183	.306		
	Total	60.630	184			
AA	Between Groups	8.251	1	8.251	15.166	.000
	Within Groups	99.561	183	.544		
	Total	107.812	184			

As pointed out in the F-test table on the difference between the attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and the future business intention of ABM and STEM students, the F-test reveals that there is no difference between the attitude toward business and business intention from both strands.

Result and Discussion

The previous studies of Abun, et.al. (2018, 2018) on the influence of entrepreneurial knowledge toward entrepreneurial intention and the influence of entrepreneurial attitude on the entrepreneurial intention found that entrepreneurial knowledge affects the entrepreneurial intention, and the entrepreneurial attitude also affects the entrepreneurial intention of students. The respondents of the two studies were all ABM grade XII students of the same schools. It was only measuring the correlation between entrepreneurial knowledge and entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial attitude and entrepreneurial intention. However, the respondents of the current study are taken from ABM and STEM grade XII students from the same school and it is not only measuring the correlation between attitude toward business and business intention but it measures the difference between the attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and their business intention. The study found that there is a correlation between the attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and their business intention. However, when it comes to measuring the difference of attitude toward business and business intention of both strands, the study found that there is no difference between ABM and STEM students when it comes to attitude toward business and business intention.

The current findings of the study complicate the discussion on the relevance of business education toward the business intention of students in the context of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The concern here is: does business or entrepreneurial education have a better influence on the attitude of students toward business and the intention to do business in the future as compared to students who are taking different courses or strands? This question is raised based on the finding of the study, that as a whole education (strands) does affect the attitude of students toward the business cognitively and effectively, however, the result of the F-test indicates that there is no significant difference between the attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and their intention to do business in the future. ABM and STEM students possess the same cognitive and affective attitude toward business and have the same intention to do business in the future. This concludes that entrepreneurial education does not

really affect or influence differently among students who are taking up ABM and STEM in terms of attitude toward business and their intention to do business in the future. Therefore, in the context of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Province, taking ABM strands do not make a difference when it comes to attitude toward business and business intention. Other courses (strands) such as STEM has/have the same level of influence on attitude toward business and have the same level of influence toward business intention or planning to do business in the future as ABM students do. This finding is not isolated from the previous finding, such as the finding of Oyewumi and Olufemi (2013) which pointed out the result of their study, that there is no significant influence of entrepreneurial knowledge on attitude toward business.

Conclusion

The purpose of the study was to measure the cognitive and affective attitude of students toward business and their business intention and determine the correlation between attitude toward business and business intention. The study found that the cognitive and affective attitude of students toward business is high and also their business intention is high. It concludes that both strands, ABM and STEM students have a high cognitive and affective attitude toward business and have a high intention to do business in the future.

Further, the study found that there is a correlation between attitude toward business and business intention and therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted. However, when it comes to the difference between the attitude of ABM and STEM students toward business and their business intention, the study found that there is no difference in cognitive and affective attitude toward business and business intention between both strands. Thus, the study concludes that attitude toward business is important to affect the business intention, however, entrepreneurial education such as ABM strands students do not make them better/higher than students from STEM in terms of attitude toward business and business intention. Both strands have the same attitude toward business and business intention.

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